

IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATION OF AUTOMATIZATION IN THE WORK OF MEDICAL LABORATORIES**Kadirkulov K.***PhD, DBA Doctoral Student**Almaty Management University, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

Laboratory automation plays a key role in improving the efficiency, accuracy, and reliability of research and analysis. The implementation of LIS reduces the time spent on routine operations and the likelihood of human error, while improving the quality of the results obtained. Thanks to the use of specialized systems and technologies in laboratories, researchers can perform analyses faster and more accurately, which in turn improves the reputation of the medical organization and attracts customers, ensuring accurate diagnosis and control of treatment results. Therefore, the relevance of implementing LIS in the practice of medical laboratories is beyond doubt.

Keywords: automation, laboratory automation, laboratory management, digitalization, healthcare management.

The market under Industry 5.0 is transforming into an ecosystem where not only companies and consumers interact, but also cyber-physical systems that form the basis of hybrid models for managing production and consumption processes. Such a market is characterized by human centricity, personalized solutions, active innovation and sustainable development. An important role in its development is played by the fifth innovation spiral (pentaspiral), which combines the interaction of business, government, science, society and the natural environment. As a result, the market is becoming a multi-layered, dynamic ecosystem that encompasses both physical goods and digital services and responds to the challenges of digital transformation [1].

Key factors influencing market development under Industry 5.0 include parameters such as the speed of adoption of digital solutions, the level of automation and robotization, and the degree of supply chain integration through digital platforms. External factors such as the tightening of economic sanctions, the need for import substitution, and the achievement of technological sovereignty also play an important role.

Laboratory automation plays an important role in modern medical practice. In recent decades there has been a rapid development of information technologies and automation methods, and their introduction into the work of clinical and diagnostic laboratories is becoming a necessity. The organization of laboratory work by means of automation methods and the introduction of specialized software allows to increase the efficiency of the process of analysis, data processing and storage, as well as to provide the necessary level of quality and accuracy of results.

The primary goal of clinical laboratories is to provide the highest possible quality of service to patients and healthcare personnel based on accurate analytical activities, high-quality documentation, and the delivery of services to the right place in the most convenient formats for patients. Achieving high quality in clinical laboratory testing is a pressing issue for both laboratory medicine and the healthcare system as a whole, as more than 80% of the information used in patient care comes from laboratories [2]. In this regard, standardization, automation, and computerization of processes carried

out in medical laboratories are key areas for the development of clinical laboratory services. Laboratory automation is aimed at increasing the role of electronic technology, computer tools and equipment, robotics, and software in process management. First and foremost, this concerns freeing laboratory personnel from routine operations and significantly speeding up the performance of analyses. Automation is the path to a real multiple increase in the productivity and efficiency of laboratory services in healthcare organizations. Specialized laboratory information systems (LIS) are becoming increasingly important in the automation process. These are software programs designed to automate all aspects of laboratory work, including test request management, data processing, sample tracking, quality control, reporting, and integration with other information systems within a healthcare organization.

LIS helps improve laboratory efficiency, ensure data accuracy and security, and enhance the overall quality of medical services provided. The implementation of LIS significantly improves the efficiency of medical laboratories through a number of factors. Let us highlight the most important ones:

1. Automation of LIS processes enables the automation of specimen receipt, processing, analysis and tracking. This eliminates the need for manual data entry and processing, which reduces the time required to perform analyses and decreases the likelihood of errors.

2. LIS results management ensures reliable management of test results, their storage and accessibility to medical staff. This facilitates timely delivery and interpretation of results.

3. Data integration: LIS can be integrated with other healthcare information systems, simplifying information exchange between different departments and improving the overall efficiency of healthcare information management.

4. Ensuring a high level of security: The implementation of LIS increases the security and confidentiality of medical data by introducing advanced encryption and access control methods [3].

It is important to note the economic impact of LIS implementation in laboratories: it reduces the cost of "paper" work and "manual" recording of test results, reduces the number of errors and the time patients wait

for test results, improves inventory management, and reduces costs by increasing laboratory efficiency and reducing human error. There are typically several basic steps involved in implementing an LIS. First, a laboratory needs analysis must be conducted to determine the basic requirements that the LIS must meet. An appropriate system is then selected. The implementation process includes installation, customization, staff training, and scheduled support. The next step is to integrate the LIS with other information systems of the medical institution (such as electronic medical records, patient management systems, etc.) [4]. This enables the exchange of information between the structural units of the medical organization.

It is also important to mention the importance of evaluating the effectiveness of LIS: the system must fully meet the needs of the laboratory and ensure optimal results. In general, the methodology for implementing and using LIS is, of course, determined by the functions assigned to a particular laboratory or laboratory service of a medical organization.

At present, an urgent task in all spheres of society is the creation of sectoral digital platforms based on different economic methods of processing large amounts of information. In the absence of multidisciplinary specialized centers, when a patient has to seek services in different institutions, it takes a lot of time to get the right results and transfer them from one specialist to another [3]. Given the shortage of specialists, a promising direction for work optimization is the creation of unified digital information platforms, which unite all large data sets of all active centers for the purpose of their subsequent transfer to the doctors of conventional medical institutions.

Studies of foreign researchers in digitalization of different healthcare institutions including medical laboratories identify key trends in the global healthcare digitalization market. It shows that the area of implementation of digital technologies in the medical industry will continue to grow in the near future due to insufficient market saturation. Local researchers make significant accent on the case of introduction of digital technologies in medical organizations in order to keep and transform data about patients. It is the most important part of healthcare management and digitalization is the only way to solve the problem of transferring data that make information flow faster and more efficient.

References

1. Isbilen Basok, B. (2020). Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence in laboratory medicine. *International Journal of Medical Biochemistry*. <https://doi.org/10.14744/ijmb.2020.81994>
2. Brinati, D., Ronzio, L., Cabitza, F., & Banfi, G. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in laboratory medicine. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 803–812. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64573-1_312
3. Baranova, T. V. (2024). Digitalization of document management system in medical organizations: Theoretical Aspect. *City Healthcare*, 5(1), 122–128. <https://doi.org/10.47619/2713-2617.zm.2024.v.5i1;122-128>
4. Rahman, M. M., & Ranjan, R. (2020). Local organizations and Healthcare Sector. *Indian Migrant Organizations*, 42–73. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190121341.003.0002>